

USING THE CASE STUDIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION THROUGH SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE

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In the context of the intercultural approach in teaching foreign languages, communicative competence is considered as a complex polymorphic concept that integrates a number of competencies. Sociolinguistic competence (SLC) is one of the most important components for both secondary schools [2] and non-linguistic and language universities. Sociolinguistic competence is the ability of a linguistic personality to organize his speech behavior adequately to communication situations, taking into account the communicative purpose, intention, social statuses, roles of communicants and the communication environment in accordance with the sociolinguistic norm and the attitudes of a particular national linguistic and cultural community [3:28]. The technology of SLC formation developed by us for secondary

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the problem of using Case Study in the formation of sociolinguistic competence at the stage of development of speech skills. The author analyzes the types of Case Study that make up this exercise, the conditions for using Case Study as part of the research method when teaching a foreign language.

school students (philological profile) involves three stages, which correspond to the stages of work on speech material proposed by E.I. Passov [4]

The study of the origin of the method of studying specific situations (cases) shows that it arose at the beginning of the XX century at the Harvard University Business School as a kind of transfer of the technology of training lawyers established by that time to the training of managers. The main feature of the method was the students' study of precedents, i.e. situations from legal or business practice that existed in the past. Special emphasis was placed on the independent work of students, during which an abyss of practical material was viewed and analyzed. By the middle of the last century, the method of studying specific situations acquired a clear

technological algorithm, and began to be actively used not only in American, but also in Western European business education. One of the definitions of the method was formulated in 1954. This is a method of teaching when students and teachers (instructors) participate in direct discussions on problems or cases of business.

Today, two classical case study schools coexist - Harvard (American) and Manchester (European). Within the framework of the first school, the purpose of the method is to teach the search for the only correct solution, the second assumes a multivariate solution to the problem. It is characteristic that the method of studying specific situations is considered as a process with the allocation of its main components such as "discussion" and "discussion". Followers of the method traditionally use Case Studies in teaching based on the principle "moving towards the truth is more important than the truth itself

An ideal concrete situation as follows:

- a typical but entertaining story of a particular business or an existing case from the history of this business;
- internal intrigue, a puzzle that needs solving;
- an abundance of information, the analysis of which is not trivial and requires the search for additional information;
- an actual problem that can give a continuation of the situation in the future.

The essence of the research method, in contrast to the method of problem presentation, is that the teacher develops and offers students problematic communicative and cognitive tasks of a

research nature. Students realize and analyze the proposed task, isolate the missing data based on the analysis, plan approaches to its solution, and justify the decision made.

We believe that it is Case Study that is designed to implement this learning method. Case Studies, considered as speech exercises, are concretized in the tasks of analyzing the sociolinguistic conditions of a communicative situation, establishing cause-and-effect relationships, establishing and eliminating errors that prevent the choice of the correct register in communication. During the performance of these tasks, students can discover fundamentally new information or explore what is already known, the main thing is that the mechanisms of creative thinking are involved and students gain research experience.

A certain value in performing creative tasks is the comparison of the studied phenomena in the native and the studied culture, the study of problems of intercultural communication and familiarization with another national linguistic and cultural community by assigning someone else's speech experience on the basis of acquired sociolinguistic knowledge, skills and abilities. Thus, at the stage of development of sociolinguistic skills, the use of Case Studies exercises ensures the presence of strategies and tactics among communicants, actualizes the relationships of communication participants, determines the productivity of statements and contributes to the development of speech activity and independence.

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